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Drainage Morphometry–Based Prioritization of Sub-Watersheds in the Kalrayan Hills (India): Morphometric Characterization, Statistical analysis, and CF–WSA Ranking

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Abstract

Objectives: To select eight sub-watersheds (WS1-WS8) in the Kalrayan Hills (Tamil Nadu, India) to conserve soil-water through the drainage morphometry and terrain attributes of the terrain using the DEM. **Method:** Slope and elevation from SRTM 30 m DEM, along with a Strahler-ordered drainage network (max order 6) and validated sub-watershed boundaries were used to calculate standard linear, areal and relief morphometric parameters. Correlation and principal component analysis were used to evaluate parameter redundancy and dominant controls. Prioritization was done using Compound Factor ranking and Weighted Sum Approach with normalized indicators. Priority classes are Very High (WS3 and WS4), High (WS5 and WS6), Moderate (WS2 and WS7), and Low (WS1 and WS8). **Findings:** Very-high priority units exhibit greater drainage development and/or relief energy, which suggests greater runoff and erosion susceptibility. Strong agreement between rankings using both methods (Spearman $r = 0.952$; $p = 0.00026$). **Novelty:** The integrated CF–WSA framework provides a rapid, decision-ready basis for phased conservation planning in data-limited mountainous watersheds.

Keywords: Sub-watershed prioritization; SRTM DEM; Compound factor; Weighted sum approach; Eastern Ghats

1 Introduction

Planning units are drainage basins and their sub-watersheds since hydrological boundaries offer a feasible means of connecting land processes to runoff, sediment delivery, and downstream effects and focusing interventions where they will be most effective⁽¹⁾. This sub-watershed emphasis is particularly critical in steep, dissected hill terrain where erosion, flash runoff, and slope instability are localized in space, and management success is determined by which units to act on sequentially⁽²⁾. A prevalent type of land degradation and a long-term cause of diminishing soil fertility and declining storage capacity in downstream channels and reservoirs is soil erosion, especially when intense rainfall is combined with disturbed land cover and concentrated

flow paths^{(3), (4)}. Conservation planning in these environments needs methods that can quickly filter various sub-watersheds on runoff and erosion susceptibility with consistent, spatially explicit indicators⁽¹⁾.

The morphometric analysis offers that foundation by converting watershed physiography and drainage-network structure into quantitative indices to capture the drainage development, runoff generation, and erosional potential⁽⁵⁾. Morphometric parameters can be systematically obtained with DEM-based and GIS-based workflows and used together with objective decision rules to rank sub-watersheds to be managed⁽⁶⁾. The present study is filling in a major weakness of conventional morphometric prioritization: redundancy of correlated variables, through multivariate statistics and multi-criteria weighting/aggregation to find dominant controls and generate robust and reproducible rankings.

Although these have been developed, parameter-based interpretation remains the limit of many of these applications, failing to provide a decision-ready prioritization that (i) combines linear, areal, and relief/terrain metrics into explicit priority classes, and (ii) assesses the consistency and consistency of the rankings produced by other scoring schemes⁽⁶⁾. The current study fills this gap in by mapping and prioritizing eight sub-watersheds (WS1-WS8) of the Kalrayan Hills based on Digital Elevation Model-derived terrain characteristics and ordered drainage network, calculating common morphometric features, eliminating redundancy and deriving key controls through correlation analysis and PCA, and generating management-relevant priority classes through two complementary prioritization models: Compound Factor ranking and a Weighted Sum Approach.

2 Methodology

2.1 Study area

The present study was carried out in the Kalrayan Hills, Tamil Nadu, India, a physio graphically distinct upland that has a high elevation gradient and drainage that is discontinuous. Figure 1a indicates the geographical location and spatial area of the basin. Digital elevation model (DEM) is a broad altitude interval of 70-1275 m above mean sea level. The slope map categorizes the steepness of the terrain into three levels: 0-9 (low; green), 10-22 (moderate), and 23-63 (high); the spatial gradient is strong because low terrain slopes are the dominant in the eastern and southeastern sector, which is the environment of the downstream/valley-floor (Figure 1b). The climate of Kalrayan Hills is monsoon-based and the majority of rainfall is concentrated within a few months, therefore, erosion is mainly caused during the wet season when short-lived storms produce large amounts of runoff. Gneiss/charnockite is the dominant rock in the area, and the alluvium is largely limited to valley bottoms⁽⁷⁾. On flatter lands, soils are clay rich whereas on hillslopes, soils are gravelly/loamy. Land use/land cover Forest, scrub/degraded wasteland, cultivated slopes and valley pockets, settlements, small tanks; forests reduce erosion, but degraded scrub, bare land, roads, and fallow fields focus runoff and provide sediment.

Fig 1. a. Study area, b. slope

2.2 Overall methodology

The overall methodology is a combination of DEM morphometric characterization using morphometrics, stream network morphometric characterization, and multi-criteria prioritization used to identify erosion prone sub-watersheds in the Kalrayan Hills. The workflow starts with SRTM DEM, watershed boundaries (WS1-WS8), and ordered drainage/stream network, harmonized to a common coordinate system under CRS harmonization, geometry/topology validation, and watershed-based clipping to provide consistent computations. Morphometric analysis is performed watershed-wise using linear, areal, and relief/terrain parameters, and results are tabulated into three thematic tables (linear, areal, terrain) and merged into a master dataset. Statistical evaluation uses correlation analysis to detect redundancy and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to identify dominant controls and reduce overlap. Prioritization is implemented using Compound Factor (CF) ranking (lower CF = higher priority) and the Weighted Sum Approach (WSA) to compute a Priority Index (PI) (higher PI = higher priority). Sensitivity testing is performed by controlled perturbation of weights ($\pm 10\%$), and rank consistency between CF and WSA is assessed using Spearman rank correlation⁽⁸⁾. Finally, sub-watersheds are assigned to management priority classes (very high, high, moderate, low), and cluster analysis is used to classify watersheds with similar morphometric signatures.

2.3 Data sources and preparation

Morphometric analysis used three spatial inputs: SRTM 30 m DEM, sub-watershed boundaries (WS1-WS8), and a Strahler-ordered drainage network (maximum order = 6). A 10 m LULC layer and DEM-derived slope were produced in Google Earth Engine (GEE). Datasets were quality-checked for unique WS IDs and valid polygon/line geometries, and processed in UTM. The drainage network was clipped to each sub-watershed to compute order-wise stream counts and lengths.

2.4 Morphometric parameterization

Morphometric characterization was conducted for each sub-watershed (WS1-WS8) using the drainage network, watershed polygons, and DEM-derived elevations. The complete mathematical expressions and original sources for all indices are presented in Table 1; therefore, this section focuses on parameter organization and interpretation. Basin geometry and shape metrics were derived from watershed polygons. Basin length (Lb) and mean basin width (Wb) (Table 1), along with basin area (A) and perimeter (P), were used to compute form and compactness indices—Form factor (Ff), shape factor (Sf), elongation ratio (Re), circularity ratio (Rc), and compactness coefficient (Cc). These measures indicate whether a basin is compact or elongated, which influences concentration time and peak discharge. Stream order (u) was after the Strahler scheme⁽⁹⁾ (Table 1). Order summarised stream length (Lu), stream number (Nu) and stream length mean (Lsm) shows the variation of segment length with order. Branching and potential structural control is described by bifurcation ratio (Rb) and mean bifurcation ratio (Rbm), and network adjustment and geomorphic stage is indicated by the length ratio of streams between successive orders (Rl) (Table 1). Areal drainage texture parameters are parameters which describe surface dissection. Drainage density (Dd) is the total length of channels per unit area and is associated with run off response and infiltration opportunity and stream frequency (Fs) is the number of stream segments per unit area⁽¹⁰⁾. The texture ratio (Rt) and drainage texture (Dt) denote the fineness of drainage and the possibility of being vulnerable to erosion (Table 1). Length of overland flow (Lg) and channel maintenance constant (C) were calculated as inverses of Dd. Relief and hypsometric parameters of vertical controls of runoff energy and sediment transport with the aid of DEM-calculated Zmax, Zmin, and Zmean. Basin relief (H) and relief ratio (Rr) are measures of relief energy and integrated steepness, relief and drainage density is represented by ruggedness number (Rn), and erosional stage is shown by hypsometric integral (HI), where higher values of HI indicate less eroded surfaces and lower values HI more denuded landscapes (Table 1).

2.5 Compound Factor (CF) prioritization

The two complementary techniques that were used to perform morphometric prioritization were Compound Factor (CF) ranking and a Weighted Sum Approach (WSA)⁽¹⁷⁾. Indicators were classified as direct (an increase in the value leads to an increase in erosion/runoff susceptibility) or inverse (an increase in the value leads to a decrease in erosion/runoff susceptibility)⁽¹⁸⁾. In the case of CF, the parameters were transformed to ranks r_{ij} (increasing with direct and decreasing with inverse indicators) and averaged to get CF_i which has lower values corresponding to higher priority (Eq. 1).

$$CF_i = (1/m) * \sum_{j=1..m} r_{ij} \quad (\text{Eq 1})$$

Table 1. Formula for calculating morphometric parameters

S. No.	Morphometric Parameter	Formula	Reference
1	Basin length (Lb)	Lb = maximum basin length	(11)
2	Mean basin width (Wb)	Wb = A / Lb	(12)
3	Basin area (A)	A = polygon area	(11)
4	Basin perimeter (P)	P = polygon perimeter	(11)
5	Length-area relation (Lar)	Lar = 1.4 × A ^{0.6}	(11)
6	Lemniscate's ratio (k)	k = Lb ² / A	(12)
7	Form factor (Ff)	Ff = A / Lb ²	(13)
8	Shape factor (Sf)	Sf = Lb ² / A	(12)
9	Elongation ratio (Re)	Re = [2√(A/π)] / Lb	(11)
10	Circularity ratio (Rc)	Rc = (4πA) / P ²	(14)
11	Compactness coefficient (Cc)	Cc = P / [2√(πA)]	(15)
12	Texture ratio (Rt)	Rt = N1 / P	(11)
13	Drainage texture (Dt)	Dt = ΣNu / P	(12)
14	Stream order (u)	Strahler stream ordering method	(16)
15	Stream number (Nu)	Nu = number of streams of order u	(12)
16	Stream length (Lu)	Lu = total length of streams of order u	(12)
17	Mean stream length (Lsm)	Lsm = Lu / Nu	(12)
18	Bifurcation ratio (Rb)	Rb = Nu / N(u+1)	(11)
19	Mean bifurcation ratio (Rbm)	Rbm = average of Rb	(16)
20	Stream length ratio (Rl)	Rl = L(u+1) / Lu	(12)
21	Drainage density (Dd)	Dd = ΣLu / A	(12)
22	Stream frequency (Fs)	Fs = ΣNu / A	(12)
23	Length of overland flow (Lg)	Lg = 1 / (2Dd)	(12)
24	Constant of channel maintenance (C)	C = 1 / Dd	(11)
25	Maximum elevation (Zmax)	Zmax = maximum DEM value	(11)
26	Minimum elevation (Zmin)	Zmin = minimum DEM value	(12)
27	Mean elevation (Zmean)	Zmean = mean DEM value	(11)
28	Basin relief (H)	H = Zmax - Zmin	(11)
29	Relief ratio (Rr)	Rr = H / Lb	(11)
30	Ruggedness number (Rn)	Rn = H × Dd	(16)
31	Hypsometric integral (HI)	HI = (Zmean - Zmin) / (Zmax - Zmin)	(11)

2.6 Weighted Sum Approach (WSA)

A continuous Priority Index (PI) was calculated using WSA. Indicators were normalized (min-max) based on direct and inverse equations (Eq. 2-Eq. 3) and summed with weights w₂ (w₂ + w₃ + ... = 1), with equal weights where the importance of the parameters was not specified (Eq. 4)⁽¹⁷⁾.

$$N_{\{ij\}} = \frac{(x_{\{ij\}} - \min(x_j))}{(\max(x_j) - \min(x_j))} \quad [Direct\ indicator] \quad (Eq\ 2)$$

$$N_{\{ij\}} = \frac{(\max(x_j) - x_{\{ij\}})}{(\max(x_j) - \min(x_j))} \quad [Inverse\ indicator] \quad (Eq\ 3)$$

$$PI_i = \sum_{\{j=1..m\}} (w_j * N_{\{ij\}}), \quad with \quad \sum_{\{j=1..m\}} w_j = 1 \quad (Eq\ 4)$$

2.7 Statistical Analysis

PCA was used to determine the leading controls and minimize multicollinearity; the variables were standardized before analysis (Eq. 5), and the components were interpreted based on eigenvalues and explained variance (Eq. 6)⁽¹⁹⁾. WSA ranks were checked by perturbing weights by 10 percent with renormalization (Eq. 7–Eq. 8) and rank shifts (Eq. 9). Spearman rank correlation (Eq. 10 and Eq. 11) was used to measure agreement between CF and WSA rankings⁽⁸⁾.

$$Z_{ij} = (x_{ij} - \mu_j) / \sigma_j \quad (\text{Eq 5})$$

$$EV_k = \lambda_k / \sum \lambda \quad (\text{Eq 6})$$

$$w'_p = w_p (1 \pm 0.10) \quad (\text{Eq 7})$$

$$w''_j = w'_j / \sum w'_j \quad (\text{Eq 8})$$

$$\Delta Rank_i = Rank_{base}(i) - Rank_{perturbed}(i) \quad (\text{Eq 9})$$

$$d_i = R_{\{CF\}}(i) - R_{\{WSA\}}(i) \quad (\text{Eq 10})$$

$$\rho = 1 - [6 \sum d_i^2] / [n(n^2 - 1)] \quad (\text{Eq 11})$$

3 Results and discussions

3.1 Sub-watersheds and stream network

Morphometric analysis and prioritization of the basin was conducted by dividing the basin into eight sub-watersheds (WS1 to WS8)⁽¹⁹⁾. Watersheds structure and their extracted streams are presented in Figure 2. WS1-WS3 are located in the western-northwestern headwaters, WS4-WS5 are located in the middle of the basin, and WS6-WS8 are located in the eastern-southeastern downstream sector where the flow is aligned with the trunk channel. The drainage is 6th order⁽⁹⁾, low-order streams dominate in headwater/interfluvies, and this is a sign of active dissection^{(12), (11)}, but higher-order channels accumulate on the central-eastern (Figure 2) trunk pathway that channels runoff to the outlet, as is frequently found in similar morphometric studies⁽²⁰⁾.

3.2 Stream Counts and Stream Frequency

First-order channels are the dominant channels in Lu in all sub-watersheds^{(12), (9)}. LuTotal: 124.16 km (WS8) to 234.17 km (WS6) WS6, WS3 and WS2 have the largest networks implying stronger runoff/sediment conveyance in steep terrain^{(11), (13), (21)} (Table 2). Lu1 and Lu2 contribute most, but anomalies—WS4 (Lu5 > Lu4) and high Lu6 in WS6, WS7, and WS8—indicate trunk dominance and ordering/segmentation effects noted in DEM-derived networks^{(12), (11), (7)} (Table 2).

3.3 Stream Length

First-order channels in all sub-watersheds^{(12), (9)} dominate Lu. LuTotal ranges from 124.16 km (WS8) to 234.17 km (WS6); WS6, WS3, and WS2 have the largest networks, implying stronger runoff and sediment conveyance in steep terrain^{(11), (13), (21)} (Table 3). Lu1 and Lu2 contribute most, but anomalies (WS4: Lu5 > Lu4; high Lu6 in WS6–WS8) indicate trunk dominance and ordering/segmentation effects noted in comparable studies^{(7), (12), (11)} (Table 2).

Fig 2. Sub-watersheds and stream network

Table 2. Stream number (Nu) and stream length (Lu, km) by order

Water-shed	Nu ₁	Nu ₂	Nu ₃	Nu ₄	Nu ₅	Nu ₆	Nu _{Total}	Lu ₁	Lu ₂	Lu ₃	Lu ₄	Lu ₅	Lu	Lu _{Total}
ws1	58	21	19	7	0	0	105	90.251	35.947	20.436	16.223	0	0	162.856
ws2	75	32	24	10	2	0	143	125.257	56.226	22.656	18.317	1.734	0	224.189
ws3	89	31	22	29	1	0	172	128.304	44.774	24.731	27.366	1.281	0	226.456
ws4	40	19	6	3	13	1	82	67.801	33.453	8.543	5.144	18.745	0.12	133.806
ws5	72	38	17	14	2	1	144	111.551	51.066	28.555	17.894	2.59	0.864	212.521
ws6	75	36	10	3	0	25	149	114.345	59.899	17.722	2.247	0	39.957	234.17
ws7	58	13	19	12	0	9	111	79.072	18.52	35.411	16.426	0	11.389	160.819
ws8	48	23	9	0	0	13	93	60.089	40.223	12.898	0	0	10.95	124.16

Nu = number of streams of order u; Lu = total stream length (km) of order u.

Table 3. Summary of Linear and Areal Morphometric Parameters

Water-shed	Rbm	Lsm	RI	Dd	Fs	Rc	Ff	Re	Lg	Cc	Area (km ²)	Perimeter (km)	Basin Length (km)	Basin Width (km)
ws1	2.194	1.665	0.587	0.702	0.453	0.422	0.301	0.619	0.712	1.539	202.982	106.073	45.479	4.463
ws2	2.769	1.414	0.439	0.83	0.529	0.505	0.443	0.751	0.603	1.407	270.2	82.005	24.686	10.945
ws3	8.51	1.247	0.514	0.824	0.626	0.55	0.385	0.7	0.607	1.348	145.463	54.231	20.627	7.052
ws4	4.101	1.359	1.0	0.92	0.564	0.622	0.342	0.66	0.544	1.268	235.772	64.271	22.621	10.423
ws5	2.869	1.335	0.424	0.901	0.611	0.717	0.461	0.766	0.555	1.181	288.964	98.328	35.496	8.141
ws6	2.284	1.462	4.683	0.81	0.516	0.376	0.229	0.54	0.617	1.632	165.199	69.614	30.413	5.432
ws7	2.016	1.457	0.826	0.792	0.547	0.227	0.098	0.353	0.631	2.1	231.86	83.097	27.748	8.356
ws8	1.778	1.319	0.613	0.752	0.563	0.428	0.179	0.477	0.665	1.528	274.859	79.224	26.735	10.281

Rbm = Mean bifurcation ratio; Lsm = Mean stream length; RI = Stream length ratio; Dd = Drainage density; Fs = Stream frequency; Rc = Circularity ratio; Ff = Form factor; Re = Elongation ratio; Lg = Length of overland flow; Cc = Compactness coefficient.

3.4 Linear Parameters

Linear morphometric indicators differentiate drainage organization among sub-watersheds^{(12), (9)}. Mean bifurcation ratio (Rbm) ranges widely from 1.778 (WS8) to 8.51 (WS3), showing great contrasts in branching; high Rbm in WS3 implies structural/lithologic or ordering/segmentation control and high runoff concentration and response variability⁽¹¹⁾. Lower Rbm in WS8 (1.778), WS7 (2.016) and WS1 (2.194) implies more homogeneous branching^{(9), (7)}. Linear parameters are summarized in Table 3. Mean stream length (Lsm) has a narrow range (1.247 - 1.665 km), with WS1 having the highest and WS3 the lowest Lsm⁽¹²⁾; lower Lsm indicates finer segmentation, and higher Lsm indicates longer reaches⁽²¹⁾. Stream length ratio (Rl) is highly variable (0.424-4.683): values <1 (WS2, WS3, WS5, WS8) indicate headwater lengths dominate, whereas WS6 shows high Rl (4.683), consistent with stronger higher-order trunk contribution, and WS4 (Rl approx. 1) indicates near-proportional scaling^{(9), (12)} (Table 3).

3.5 Areal parameters

Areal morphometric parameters indicate strong contrasts in basin size, drainage efficiency, and shape among the sub-watersheds^{(7), (9), (21)}. Basin area ranges from 145.463 km² (WS3) to 288.964 km² (WS5), with WS8 (274.859 km²) and WS2 (270.200 km²) also large (Table 3). Drainage density (Dd) varies from 0.702 (WS1) to 0.920 (WS4), with high values also in WS5 (0.901) and WS2 (0.830), implying stronger dissection and faster runoff concentration in WS4–WS5 under similar forcing^{(12), (13)}. Stream frequency (Fs) shows the same tendency (0.453 in WS1 to 0.626 in WS3), with high Fs in WS5 (0.611) and WS4 (0.564), consistent with finer drainage texture⁽¹²⁾ (Table 3). Shape metrics further explain response differences: Rc ranges from 0.227 (WS7) to 0.717 (WS5) and Ff from 0.098 (WS7) to 0.461 (WS5), indicating WS5 (and WS4/WS2) are more compact and likely to show shorter concentration times and sharper peaks than elongated basins such as WS7 and WS6^{(9), (11), (14)} (Table 3). Re confirms this contrast (0.353 in WS7 to 0.766 in WS5), while Lg (0.544 in WS4 to 0.712 in WS1) implies reduced sheet-flow travel and quicker channel entry in WS4–WS5^{(12), (13)}. Compactness coefficient (Cc) ranges from 1.181 (WS5) to 2.100 (WS7), again identifying WS5/WS4 as most compact and WS7 as least compact^{(14), (15)} (Table 3).

3.6 Terrain Parameters

Relief metrics show strong contrasts in terrain energy and geomorphic stage across the sub-watersheds^{(9), (11)}. Basin relief (H) ranges from 117 m (WS8) to 1121 m (WS6); high-relief basins (WS6, WS4, WS3, WS1) imply stronger slope-driven runoff and erosive competence^{(11), (21)}. Relief ratio (Rr) is highest in WS4 (0.0514), indicating the steepest basin-scale gradient, while WS8 (0.0038) and WS7 (0.0127) are comparatively gentle^{(9), (11)}, consistent with faster runoff formation and higher stream power in WS4 (and secondarily WS3/WS1) under similar rainfall⁽¹²⁾. Ruggedness number (Rn) further isolates high-erosion potential basins: WS4 (976.12) and WS6 (908.01) are highest, whereas WS8 (87.98) is lowest, indicating a low-energy setting^{(9), (12), (11), (21)}. Hypsometric integral (HI) suggests geomorphic stage differences, with WS8 highest (0.517; less eroded) and WS6 (0.164) and WS2 (0.197) lowest (more mature/denuded)^{(9), (11)}. Overall, terrain measures identify WS4 and WS6 as most topographically aggressive (high H and very high Rn, with WS4 also highest Rr), implying higher runoff responsiveness and erosion susceptibility, whereas WS8 is least active to erosion and WS2/WS5/WS7 are intermediate-to-low⁽¹²⁾.

3.7 Normalized morphometric response of eight sub-watersheds (linear, areal and relief parameters)

Figure 3 compares 0–1 normalized linear (Rbm, Lsm, Rl), areal (Dd, Fs, Rc, Re, Lg), and relief (H, Rn) indices, showing strong inter-watershed heterogeneity in drainage structure, basin form, and terrain control^{(9), (12), (11)}. High Dd/Fs coincide with low Lg, implying shorter flow paths and quicker runoff routing, whereas low Dd/Fs correspond to higher Lg and weaker runoff response^{(12), (13)}. Shape metrics (Rc, Re) indicate that compact basins concentrate runoff faster than elongated ones, supporting sub-watershed-specific prioritization rather than treating the basin as homogeneous^{(9), (11), (14)}. Variations in Rbm, Lsm and Rl represent differences in branching and scaling of segments associated with structural/geomorphic controls and routing efficiency^{(7), (9), (12), (11)}. Peaks in H and Rn are indicative of high energy terrain, and when combined with high Dd/Fs (and low Lg) imply higher erosion and sediment yield potential, consistent with similar morphometric risk interpretations^{(9), (21)}. Overall, Figure 3 highlights the integration of network structure, drainage efficiency, basin form, and severity of terrain for prioritization^{(19), (22)}.

Fig 3. Normalized morphometric response profiles of eight sub-watersheds (linear, areal and relief parameters)

3.8 Compound factor ranking

The CF approach classifies the eight sub-watersheds by taking an average of parameter ranks (1 = most erosion-critical) for key morphometric indicators^{(19), (5), (23)}. Lower CF hence represents higher priority since it represents consistently high rankings across multiple controls. CF values range from 2.583 to 5.833, which clearly distinguishes sub-watersheds (Table 4): the lowest CF (2.583) represents the highest priority unit and the next is CF = 3.583, mid-priority units are clustered around CF approximately 4.08–4.75, and the highest CF values (5.083–5.833) represent the lowest priority^{(12), (24)}. The full CF ranking is reported in Table 4.

Table 4. Compound factor and Weighted Sum Ranking

Rbm Rank	Dd Rank	Fs Rank	Rn Rank	H Rank	Rr Rank	Ff Rank	Re Rank	Rc Rank	Lg Rank	Cc Rank	Compound Factor	Priority Index	Priority Class
2	1	3	1	2	1	5	5	7	1	2	2.583	0.338	Low
1	4	1	3	3	2	6	6	6	4	3	3.583	0.441	Moderate
5	5	7	2	1	4	3	3	2	5	7	4.083	0.630	Very High
3	2	2	6	7	6	8	8	8	2	1	4.583	0.717	Very High
4	3	6	5	5	5	7	7	5	3	4	4.750	0.507	High
7	6	5	7	6	7	1	1	1	6	8	5.083	0.580	High
6	8	8	4	4	3	4	4	3	8	6	5.500	0.501	Moderate
8	7	4	8	8	8	2	2	4	7	5	5.833	0.342	Low

3.9 Weighted Sum Approach (WSA)-Derived Priority Index and Priority Classes

The Weighted Sum Approach (WSA) resulted in a Priority Index (PI) of 0.338 - 0.717, classifying sub-watersheds into Very High (0.630, 0.717), High (0.507, 0.580), Moderate (0.441, 0.501), and Low (0.338, 0.342) classes⁽²⁰⁾. The priority map (Figure 4)

reveals a clear spatial pattern with Very High (WS3-WS4) clustering in the north-central, High (WS5-WS6) in the central belt, Moderate (WS2-WS7) in transition zones and Low (WS1-WS8) in the NW margin and far-eastern downstream sector, consistent with spatial contrasts in drainage development and relief controls^{(9), (12)}. WS3 - WS4 are prioritized as they combine the good drainage-network development and/or high terrain energy, mechanism widely reported in morphometric erosion-screening studies^{(12), (9)}. WS3 has the highest Nu_Total (172) and high Lu_Total (226.456 km) plus very high Rbm (8.51), suggesting strong structural/ordering control and rapid flow concentration^{(7), (11)}. WS4 has high Dd (0.92) and low Lg (0.544) with very high relief metrics (H = 1061 m; Rr = 0.0514; Rn = 976.12), indicating short runoff travel paths and high stream power^{(13), (12), (21)}. High-priority WS5-WS6 show substantial network totals (WS5: Nu_Total = 144; Lu_Total = 212.521 km; WS6: Nu_Total = 149; Lu_Total = 234.17 km) and elevated relief energy, with WS6 especially rugged (H = 1121 m; Rn = 908.01)^{(11), (21)}. Moderate WS2-WS7 reflect comparatively lower terrain forcing: WS2 remains well-drained but with moderate relief (H = 666 m; Rr = 0.0269; Rn = 552.78), while WS7 has lower Rr (0.0127) despite moderate H (580 m), implying weaker slope-driven energy than the Very High/High group^{(12), (11)} (Table 4).

Fig 4. Watershed priority

3.10 Correlation Analysis

Strong multicollinearity is evident in the correlation structure (Figure 5a). Drainage density (Dd) is almost perfectly inversely related to length of overland flow (Lg) and channel maintenance (C) ($Dd-Lg r = -0.996$; $Dd-C r = -0.996$), while Lg and C are perfectly correlated ($r = 1.000$), confirming they carry the same information because both are direct functions of Dd^{(12), (13)}. Basin-shape indices also cluster: Ff-Re is near-perfect ($r = 0.994$), both relate strongly to Rc ($Rc-Ff r = 0.863$; $Rc-Re r = 0.868$), and Cc is strongly negative with these measures ($Cc-Rc r = -0.957$; $Cc-Ff r = -0.864$; $Cc-Re r = -0.894$), so including all of Rc, Ff, Re, and Cc can overweight a single “compactness” signal unless redundancy is controlled^{(11), (14)}. Network-size measures similarly co-vary: Lu and Nu correlate strongly ($r = 0.948$), indicating a shared network-magnitude dimension^{(9), (12)}. Relief indices form another coherent block, with H correlated with Rr ($r = 0.875$) and especially with Rn ($r = 0.978$), and Rr-Rn also strong ($r = 0.919$), implying ruggedness largely tracks relief and basin-scale steepness^{(9), (11), (21)}. In contrast, HI is comparatively independent but shows moderate negative links with Lu, Dd, and Rn and positive with Lg/C, consistent with more developed, rugged drainage being associated with lower HI (more eroded/mature)^{(9), (11)}.

3.11 Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

PCA was used to reduce redundancy among morphometric parameters. The scree plot (Figure 5b) shows an elbow around PC3, with PC1-PC3 explaining 43%, 21%, and 13% of variance ($\approx 77\%$ cumulative), indicating that most variability can be represented by three orthogonal controls and that higher PCs contribute little beyond noise or highly specific effects⁽¹⁹⁾. Retaining PC1-PC3 is therefore sufficient for interpreting dominant controls and limiting multicollinearity in prioritization, consistent with the strong correlation clusters observed (Dd-Lg/C and Rc-Ff-Re). PCA indicates that a few physically meaningful gradients control the morphometric dataset and that several parameters are redundant because they co-load on the same components. PC1 represents a drainage-efficiency and basin-form axis, loading positively on Dd and shape metrics (Rc, Ff, Re) and negatively on Lg, C, and Cc. PC1 indicates that denser, more compact/circular basins tend to have shorter overland-flow paths and lower channel-maintenance needs, consistent with the inverse dependence of Lg and C on Dd and the opposition between Rc and Cc^{(12), (11), (13), (14)}. PC2 represents terrain control, loading strongly on H and Rn, showing that topographic dissection contributes variability independent of planform geometry and drainage efficiency^{(9), (11), (21)}. PC3 links hypsometric state with basin form (HI and elongation/shape positive, Cc negative), implying partial coupling between hypsometry and form⁽⁹⁾. PC4 captures network size (Nu and Lu), showing that they describe the same dimension^{(9), (12)} PC5 and PC6 isolate branching and scaling (Rbm and RL) which indicate bifurcation structure and order wise length scaling add information not explained by size, relief or basin geometry⁽⁹⁾.

Fig 5. a. Correlation matrix heat map, b. Scree plot

4 Conclusion

A distinction of sub-watersheds is evident in the drainage structure and the terrain/land controls (morphometric analyses) allows for erosion priority zoning in the Kalrayan Hills. Consistent CF and WSA outcomes (high, statistically significant rank agreement) were found to indicate that morphometry-based prioritization is robust for assessing conservation targets where long-term hydro meteorological records are lacking. Priorities form a coherent spatial pattern: Very High in the north central sub-watersheds (WS3 - WS4), High in the central belt (WS5 - WS6), Moderate in transitional units (WS2 - WS7) and Low in peripheral downstream/NW sectors (WS1, WS8) Supporting phased implementation and efficient resource-requirements allocation Management priorities should be WS3 - WS4 first by runoff-velocity and sediment-detachment controls (contour/graded bunds, vegetative barriers, gully stabilization, and reach-appropriate check dams) followed by WS5 - WS6 by slope-length WS2 - WS7 can be effectively subjected to moderate interventions focusing on the strengthening of the land cover and the drainage line treatment in a localised area, while WS1 and WS8 are suitable for maintenance actions (protection of the vegetation and treatment on site only at the locations where the active erosion is confirmed). Future work should validate priorities based on event-based erosion proxies (sediment yield, gully inventories, reservoir siltation), try higher resolution DEMs, and combine soil/land use modelling (e.g., RUSLE inputs) to create composite erosion risk assessments. Transferability can be enhanced by uncertainty analysis of parameter extraction (stream-threshold sensitivity, DEM-resolution effects) and multi-temporal land use change evaluation.

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A. Alagappa Moses is a *Research Scholar* and T. Rakesh Sharma serves as an *Assistant Professor*.

References

- 1) Liu W, Shi C, Li H, X. Land use and land cover change-induced changes of sediment connectivity and their effects on sediment yield in a catchment on the Loess Plateau in China. *Catena*. 2021;207:105688. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2021.105688>.
- 2) Jothimani M, Panda PK, Karuppannan S, Shano L, Getahun E, Dawit Z. Mapping Soil Erosion Vulnerability in the Upper Blue Nile River Basin, Ethiopia: Integrating Drainage Morphometrics and Geospatial Analysis. 2025. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-84698-4_10.
- 3) Alemayehu S, Getahun E, Jothimani M. Spatial and temporal analysis of soil erosion and sediment yield in the Shafe watershed, main Ethiopian rift region: integrating RUSLE model, GIS, and remote sensing techniques. *Discover Sustainability*. 2025;6:584. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43621-025-01427-y>.
- 4) Li H, Guan Q, Sun Y, Wang Q, Liang L, Du Q. Spatiotemporal analysis of the quantitative attribution of soil water erosion in the upper reaches of the Yellow River Basin based on the RUSLE-TLSD model. *Catena*. 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2022.106081>.
- 5) Jothimani M, Panda PK, Shano L, Getahun E, Dawit Z. Application of MCDA-GIS Methods for Soil Erosion Susceptibility Mapping in the Upper Blue Nile River Basin, Ethiopia. 2025. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-82311-4_6.
- 6) Ghimire S, Lu Y, Wang Y. An improved framework to prioritize sub-watersheds: Construction of Watershed Morphometric Composite Index (WMCI) for mountain soil conservation. *Ecological Indicators*. 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2025.113817>.
- 7) Sakthivel R, Raj N, Sivasankar V, Sivasankar V, Akhila P, Omine K. Geo-spatial technique-based approach on drainage morphometric analysis at Kalrayan Hills, Tamil Nadu, India. *Applied Water Science*. 2019;9:1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13201-019-0899-7>.
- 8) Gooch J. Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient. 2006. <https://doi.org/10.1002/0471667196.ess2499.pub2>.
- 9) Strahler AN. Quantitative geomorphology of drainage basin and channel networks. 1964.
- 10) Gadakh S, Wandre SS, Patil MA, Jadhav A, Shinde V, Ghatge J, et al. Quantitative analysis of morphometric parameters for prioritization of Warana River basin using remote sensing and GIS. *Journal of Agriculture and Ecology*. 2024;18:32–38. <https://doi.org/10.58628/JAE-2418-105>.
- 11) Schumm SA. Evolution of drainage systems and slopes in badlands at Perth Amboy, New Jersey. *Geological Society of America Bulletin*. 1956;67(5):597–646.
- 12) Horton RE. Erosional development of streams and their drainage basins: hydrophysical approach to quantitative morphology. *Geological Society of America Bulletin*. 1945;56:275–370.
- 13) Horton RE. Drainage-basin characteristics. *Transactions of the American Geophysical Union*. 1932;13(1):350–361.
- 14) Miller VC. A quantitative geomorphic study of drainage basin characteristics on the Clinch Mountain area, Virginia and Tennessee. 1953.
- 15) Gravelius H. Flusskunde. Morphometry of Drainage Basins. 1914.
- 16) Strahler AN, Chow VT. Quantitative geomorphology of drainage basins and channel networks. 1964.
- 17) Articleinf O, Dahiphale P, Singh M, Yousuf A. Watershed prioritization based on morphometric analysis in Kandi region of Punjab using geospatial technology. *Indian Journal of Soil Conservation*. 2025. <https://doi.org/10.59797/ijsc.v50.i1.153>.
- 18) Aniya L, Sora TR. Prioritization of sub-watersheds for erosion-prone identification: A study of Kiile watershed, Arunachal Pradesh, India. *Asian Journal of Geographical Research*. 2025;8(4):195–223. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajgr/2025/v8i4330>.
- 19) Sharma N, Kaushal A, Yousuf A, Kaur S, Sharda R, Singh S, et al. Prioritization of erosion susceptible watersheds using morphometric analysis and PCA approach: A case study of lower Sutlej River basin of Indian Punjab. *Watershed Ecology and the Environment*. 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wsee.2023.08.002>.
- 20) Jothimani M, Abebe A, Dawit Z. Mapping of soil erosion-prone sub-watersheds through drainage morphometric analysis and weighted sum approach: a case study of the Kulfo River basin, Rift valley, Arba Minch, Southern Ethiopia. *Modeling Earth Systems and Environment*. 2020;6:2377–2389. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40808-020-00820-y>.
- 21) Melton MA. An analysis of the relations among elements of climate, surface properties, and geomorphology. 1957.
- 22) Nitharwal TR, Lal VC, Mishra AP, Karvendu KK, Singh R, Kumari G, et al. Sub-watershed prioritization of Chambal River Basin using morphometric and topo-hydrological parameters. *Journal of Environmental & Earth Sciences*. 2025;7(5):117–129. <https://doi.org/10.30564/jees.v7i5.8463>.
- 23) Abdul-Rahaman S, Ajeez SA, Aruchamy S, Jegankumar R. Prioritization of sub watershed based on morphometric characteristics using fuzzy analytical hierarchy process and geographical information system—a study of Kallar watershed, Tamil Nadu. *Aquatic Procedia*. 2015;4:1322–1330. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aqpro.2015.02.172>.
- 24) Sahu SR, Rawat KS, Singh SK, Gupta KK. Analysis of drainage morphometry and spectral indices using earth observation datasets in Palar River basin, India. *Discover Geoscience*. 2024;2:41. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44288-024-00038-w>.